

Effect of graphene grains size on the microwave electromagnetic shielding effectiveness of graphene/polymer multilayers

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Abstract. The influence of CVD graphene grain size on the electromagnetic (EM) shielding performance of graphene/polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) multilayers in K_a -band was studied both experimentally and theoretically. We found that increasing the average graphene grain size from 20 to 400 microns does not change the EM properties of heterostructures consisting of graphene layers sandwiched between sub-micron thick PMMA spacers. The independence of EM interference shielding effectiveness on the graphene grain size between 20 to 400 microns allows one to use cheaper (or more convenient regimes of CVD) graphene samples with low crystallinity and small grain size in the development of new graphene-based passive electromagnetic devices operated at high frequencies.

Keywords: microwaves, electromagnetic shielding, graphene grain size, heterostructure, CVD graphene.

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1 Introduction

The quality of wafer-size graphene is still remaining the major bottleneck in the fabrication and mass production of novel photonic and optoelectronic devices relying on unique properties of Dirac electrons.¹⁻⁴ This is because the presence of defects, grain boundaries, multiple domains, impurities and other irregularities in the graphene sheet inevitably affects the carriers mobility, provoking thereby a deterioration of the electronic and optical properties. Among the variety of graphene fabrication techniques, such as mechanical exfoliation of graphite,⁵ sublimation of epitaxial SiC⁶ and catalyct-assisted chemical vapor deposition (CVD),^{2,7-10} the CVD is the most promising **route** for scalable graphene fabrication. However, the polycrystalline character of CVD graphene implies electron scattering on boundaries between adjacent crystallites that strongly influence the transport,¹¹ thermal and electrical properties, as well as the contact resistance of the

graphene/metal interface, thus reducing the performance of high-frequency graphene electronic devices.^{12,13} In particular, it has been shown that grain boundaries result in prominent weak localization effects indicative of inter-valley charge carrier scattering that impedes electrical transport in CVD graphene.¹⁴ This makes it difficult to employ CVD graphene in practical electronic components and devices capable to generate, detect and process electromagnetic (EM) signals.

On the other hand, one may expect that the ability of graphene for absorbing electromagnetic radiations at high frequency be less sensitive (in comparison with transport properties) to the grain size. Such an intuitive conclusion is based on the fact that under EM radiations with wavelength of about 1 cm the micron-sized graphene grains are coupled not only electrically, but also electromagnetically.

Recently, we demonstrated that graphene/polymer (polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)) multilayers can provide an efficient far-field shielding against microwave radiations, allowing one to achieve up to 50 % absorption of the incident radiation.¹⁵ The goal of this paper is to investigate both experimentally and theoretically the influence of CVD graphene grain size on the electromagnetic shielding performance of such sandwich structures. In a broader sense, we aim at revealing the effects of the CVD graphene quality on the electromagnetic properties of passive electromagnetic devices.

2 Modelling

The Rigorous Coupled-Wave Analysis (RCWA) method¹⁶ has been applied to theoretically explore the role of graphene grain sizes in the total high-frequency electromagnetic shielding performance of graphene-based multilayers. This method is well adapted to plane-stratified systems with a periodic variation of dielectric permittivity in the lateral directions.^{17,18}

The frequency used in the calculations was 30 GHz (1 cm wavelength in vacuum), the PMMA/graphene multilayer was treated as a stack of dielectric slabs (PMMA spacers, 100 nm thick, permittivity at the working frequency of 2.6¹⁸), alternating with graphene layers and deposited on a SiO₂ substrate with permittivity 3.7.¹⁸ Each graphene layer was treated as ultra-thin conducting medium (thickness $d_{graph} = 0.34nm$) with complex bulk dielectric function $\epsilon(\omega) = 2.5 + i\frac{\sigma_{2D}}{\epsilon_0\omega d_{graph}}$. In that expression, σ_{2D} is the sheet conductivity of graphene, which for GHz frequency is dominated by intra-band transitions.^{19,20} For a given sample, the sheet conductivity of graphene varies only weakly with frequency up to the THz regime.^{21,22} We took the value $\sigma_{2D}/\epsilon_0c = 0.37$ used in our previous works (Ref. 17)

The electromagnetic modes were calculated in each layer of a graphene/PMMA heterostructure and then analytically propagated through the system by applying appropriate boundary conditions at each interface. Transmission (T) and reflection (R) coefficients were retrieved from the Poynting vector computed in both incidence and emergence media. The absorbance (A) followed from $A = 1 - T - R$.

The polycrystalline character of CVD graphene introduces boundaries between adjacent grains. The width of those grain boundaries is estimated to be 3 - 5 nm.²³ In the present simulations, random grains were created with average size of 20 μm (Fig. 1 a) and 400 μm (Fig. 1 b). **The grain boundaries between adjacent grains were implemented with a width of approximately 5.5 nm and a dielectric permittivity of 1. This stands for the worse possible electrical situation, since the grain boundaries are therefore not made of a conducting material anymore.**

The modeling results for absorption, transmission and reflection provided by graphene/PMMA sandwiches consisting of graphene with different grain size are presented in Fig. 1c. The curves obtained for the two kinds of graphene can barely be distinguished, demonstrating that the electro-

Fig 1 Graphene grain patchwork for small ($20 \mu\text{m}$) (a) and large ($400 \mu\text{m}$) (b) graphene grains drawn from experiment and transposed to RCWA calculations to investigate the effects of grain boundaries on the electromagnetic properties of a graphene/PMMA multilayer. The blue lines, 5.5 nm thick, have a dielectric permittivity of 1, the rest has the permittivity of graphene. (c) Absorbance (A), reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) of graphene/PMMA sandwich structures composed of N graphene layers in case of graphene made of small (red lines) and large (blue lines) grains.

magnetic response is not sensitive to the grain size. In both case, the grain size are smaller than the incident wavelength of **1 cm in vacuum, which becomes 0.63 cm (a factor of $1/\sqrt{2.6}$ smaller) in the heterostructure** and an effective medium theory can be used to describe the graphene dielectric permittivity with different grain size. As long as the total area occupied by the boundaries remains negligible compared to the total area occupied by the grains, the grain boundaries have no effects on the electromagnetic properties of graphene. Those results can be compared with those for a few percentages of small air holes in the graphene sheets that already proved not affecting the electromagnetic properties of graphene.¹⁷

3 Experimental details

3.1 Samples fabrication and quality control

On the experimental side, sandwich structures based on graphene with different grain size were produced. The graphene was synthesized by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) at atmospheric pressure. The copper foil (99.9 % purity; 50 μm thick; 1 cm^2) was first sonicated in acetone for 15 min, then in isopropanol for 15 min and finally deoxidized in acetic acid (99.5 % purity) at 35 °C for 10 min. Next, it was inserted into a quartz tube inside a hot-wall furnace whose temperature was set at 1050 °C. In order to provide different size of grains the graphene (GRA) deposition was made in two regimes:

- Samples with small grains (about 20 μm) were produced as follows: (1) a 1-hour time annealing of the Cu foil under argon (500 sccm, 99.9 % purity) and hydrogen (20 sccm, 99.9 % purity); (2) graphene growth by filling the chamber with 1 sccm of diluted methane (5 % in argon) for 1 hour; (3) fast cooling of the sample in the same gas mixture.
- **The "large grain size" samples were grown identically as for the small-grain samples with one difference in the Cu annealing step. For the first 30 min, the annealing was in argon flow (500 sccm), while during the following 30 min, the annealing was with an argon/hydrogen mixture (500/20 sccm). Thereby, during the first 30 min of the annealing, the copper foil surface was slightly oxidized thanks to residual impurities in the argon flow,²⁴ the so-called oxidative annealing was applied.^{25,26}**

To determine the grain size, the synthesis of test samples was stopped before graphene covered the whole copper substrate. The morphology and structure of the graphene domains were con-

Fig 2 SEM images of graphene hexagonal domains corresponding to 20 μm -GRA (a) and 400 μm -GRA (c) samples, when the synthesis was stopped before graphene covered the whole copper substrate. (b), (d) optical images of graphene samples after chemical treatment obtained according to technique proposed in Ref. 27. The disks drawn with a thin dotted line in (b) and (d) indicate the graphene domains in case of small and large grain size samples, respectively

trolled by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM, JEOL JSM-7500 F). As can be seen in Fig. 2 a and c, the graphene domains have a hexagonal shape with uniform color contrast and average lateral size around 20 μm (20 μm -GRA) and 400 μm (400 μm -GRA), respectively.

Additionally, after CVD deposition graphene grain boundaries were visualized by using a simple technique proposed by S. Yu et al.:²⁷ basic permanganate solution was used as an oxidant and graphene grain boundaries were observed by **means of optical microscopy (MI-1, Planar, Belarus, the measurements were done in the reflection mode with a with a 100 \times and 80 \times objectives)**. Fig. 2 b and d show typical images of graphene samples with domain size of 20 μm and 400 μm , respectively. One can observe in Fig. 2 that images of the graphene grains provided by optical microscope and SEM give the same size of the graphene grains.

Fig 3 Raman maps of the intensity ratio of D- and G-bands over a $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}$ area of $20 \mu\text{m}$ -GRA (a) and $400 \mu\text{m}$ -GRA (d), respectively. Raman maps of the intensity ratio of 2D- and G-bands over a $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}$ area of $20 \mu\text{m}$ -GRA (b) and $400 \mu\text{m}$ -GRA (e), respectively. (c), (f) Raman spectra corresponding to the different regions marked with dots in (b) and (e). Spectra labelled 1 in (c) and 3 in (f) are typical of graphene monolayer. All spectra were normalized on the G band peak amplitude

Raman mapping was further used to analyze the quality and uniformity of the graphene sheet. For this purpose, graphene films were transferred onto Si wafers with a 300 nm thick SiO_2 native oxide overlayer using the conventional "PMMA-mediated" technique.²⁸ Measurements were performed using Raman spectrometer combined with a confocal microscope Nanonder High End (Tokyo Instruments) with a 600 lines/mm grating and 532 nm laser excitation. Spectra were collected using a $50\times$ objective and at low power (20 mW) to reduce sample degradation (Fig. 3). From the analysis of Raman maps of the intensity ratio of 2D- ($\sim 2675 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ **with the typical FWHM value of 35-40 cm^{-1}**) and G- ($\sim 1581 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ **with the typical FWHM value of 17-21 cm^{-1}**) bands, and Raman spectra from different points, it can be concluded that the largest part of both samples is graphene monolayer but small multilayer islands are also present on the surface.

The sandwich-like graphene/PMMA structures were produced using the procedure described elsewhere.¹⁵ **Briefly, the CVD graphene layer was spin coated with 100 nm-thick PMMA layer, after that, the Cu substrate was wet etched in ferric chloride and the obtained graphene / PMMA film was washed in distilled water and transferred onto a 0.53 mm-thick fused silica substrate. In order to fabricate sandwich multilayers containing several graphene sheets separated by PMMA layers, the same procedure was repeated several times, each newly-produced graphene/PMMA unit being deposited on top of the stack obtained at the previous step**

It is worth noting that **depending on the experimental conditions** 4 -7-layered graphene/PMMA heterostructure **reaches its** the maximum possible 50 % absorbance in free space and waveguide geometry. Thereby, measurements on samples with three and six graphene layers allow us to visualize the influence of the graphene crystalline size of the EM shielding performance when the number of layers is close to the optimal one.

3.2 Electromagnetic response measurements

Microwave measurements in the K_a -band (26-36 GHz) were made with a scalar network analyzer R2-408R (ELMIKA, Vilnius, Lithuania). The IEC 62431:2008(E) standard for reflectivity measurements of EM materials was used. The EM response of sample was measured as ratios of transmitted/input (S_{21}) and reflected/input (S_{11}) signals after insertion of the specimen into the transmission line (rectangular waveguide) perpendicular to wave propagation. The lateral dimensions of the samples fitted precisely the waveguide $7.2 \times 3.4 \text{ mm}^2$ cross section.

4 Experimental results and discussion

The measured results for graphene/polymer sandwich heterostructures (20 μm -GRA and 400 μm -GRA) consisting of three and six graphene/PMMA units are presented in Fig. 4. As it was expected and proved by theory the EM properties of samples produced from the graphene of small and large grain size are the same for both three- and six-layered graphene/PMMA sandwiches. As it follows from Fig. 4 b the total EM shielding effectiveness ($SE = -20 \log(S_{21})$) of graphene/polymer sandwiches in K_a -band varies in the range of 9 - 7 dB and 13 - 11 dB for 3 and 6 graphene layers, respectively, **which is in good agreement with the previously reported data.^{15,29,30}** In particular, in Ref. 29, shielding effectiveness of graphene monolayer and multilayer structures has been investigated. It was shown that the SE of monolayer graphene is 2.27 dB and the average SE values of double- and triple-layer graphene were 4.13 dB and 6.91 dB, respectively. In Ref. 30, it was demonstrate that the SE value of reduced graphene oxide (RGO) sheets interleaved between polyetherimide with the number of RGO layers to achieves 6.37 dB for double-PEI/RGO multilayer. It is important to note that each graphene/PMMA sandwich is less than 1 micron thick (**the overall thickness of samples with 3 and 6 graphene/PMMA layers was 300-400 nm and 600-700 nm, respectively**), still the level of EM power attenuation is similar to that observed for conventional polymer composites loaded with 5-10 wt. % of graphene nanoplatelets or carbon nanotubes^{31,32} but with overall thickness of fraction of mm, namely a factor of 1000 thicker.

Our experiments and theoretical findings in the K_a microwave band correlate well with recent results on the electrical properties of graphene at THz frequencies. Specifically, Buron et al have shown that graphene layer with lateral size of up to hundreds of microns grown on single crystal

Fig 4 (a) Frequency dependence of S_{11} and S_{21} for graphene/polymer heterostructures **on silica substrate** consisting graphene with small and large **grain size**. **Measured S_{11} and S_{21} for pure silica substrate (0.5 mm thickness) are shown inset.** (b) **The average SE of graphene/polymer heterostructures as function of the number of graphene layers at 30 GHz.**

copper foil is electrically continuous at 1-15 THz.²²

5 Conclusions

The reported weak sensitivity of the results to the grain size of graphene together with high shielding effectiveness observed for graphene-based flexible thin multilayers opens an avenue for the development of a scalable protocol of cost-efficient production of ultra-light optically transparent EM shields. Shielding layers composed of inexpensive polycrystalline CVD graphene consisting of small graphene domains can be transferred to commercial applications.

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